

A PARAMETER TO INDICATE CENTRIFUGAL IMPELLER EXIT BPF NOISE LEVELS

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ABSTRACT

The centrifugal compressor design involves trade-offs involving several geometric parameters. The goals of the design are generally multi-disciplinary and multi-dimensional. Recent legislative demands on the heavy-duty truck industry push the limits for efficiency and noise. Acoustic measurements indicate that the exit noise generated from the rotor is the major contributor to the tonal BPF noise levels. Advanced CFD techniques such as URANS and LES are employed to quantify noise levels. However, these methods demand more resources and time. The objective of this study is to identify a simple parameter that can indicate the impeller exit tonal Blade Pass Frequency (BPF) noise of a centrifugal compressor using RANS simulations and validate the same with experimental measurements. This work introduces a new parameter called acoustic crest factor that can indicate the tonal BPF noise from the impeller exit using the circumferential variation of static pressure at the impeller exit. Acoustic crest factor can predict the trends observed in normalized sound pressure level values measured at the impeller exit for both full and splitter-blade wheels. This is further validated by using acoustic crest factor to rank four different compressor impellers tested in an anechoic chamber with sound power level measurements. This shows that the identified parameter 'Acoustic Crest Factor' could be used as a design tool to rank designs based on acoustic signatures and also as an objective function for optimization.

Keywords: Centrifugal, Impeller, BPF, Noise, Acoustic crest factor

NOMENCLATURE

PR	Pressure Ratio
TT	Total-to-total
P_{uxh}	Unsteady Static Pressure at hub at station x
P_{0x}	Total Pressure at station x
T_{0x}	Total Temperature at station x
p	Static pressure
ρ	Density
t	Time
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
ω	Angular velocity in radians per second
RMS	Root Mean Square

Subscripts

TT	Total-to-total
t	Tangential
ref	Reference
abs	Absolute frame of reference
rel	Relative frame of reference
1	Inlet measurement section plane
2	Impeller inlet section plane
3	Diffuser inlet-unsteady pressure measurement
4	Diffuser inlet plane
5	Diffuser outlet plane
6	Diffuser outlet plane-cover flange
7	Volute throat plane
8	Volute exit plane
9	Outlet measurement section plane

1. INTRODUCTION

The centrifugal compressor design and analysis involves several geometric parameters. The goals of the design are generally multi-faceted (efficiency and range) and multi-disciplinary (aerodynamics, aeromechanics and thermodynamics). Recent noise legislations demand much quieter engines in the heavy-duty truck industry, while maintaining higher efficiency levels and range of operation. This further complicates the centrifugal compressor design space with additional objectives and constraints. With such level of complexity, evaluation of acoustics requires high-fidelity simulations or measurements, both of which consume time and resources. Experimental measurements are preferred in the industry but prototyping, testing and data analysis takes several months.

Research literature related to tonal noise of centrifugal compressors could be broadly classified into three areas, namely, experimental, analytical and high-fidelity simulations. Numerous studies are related to experimental measurements in acoustic test cells to quantify tonal noise sources [1]. Detailed experimental methods provide valid data for noise quantification but are time-consuming and expensive [2]. Another limitation of such tests is the limited range of operation of turbochargers in the acoustic cell, as they are driven by a base engine that does not operate at all off-design conditions. Performing design studies or optimization trade-offs with such detailed measurements require designing, prototyping and testing of components, which can be expensive and cumbersome.

On the other hand, advanced CFD techniques such as Large Eddy Simulations (LES) and Unsteady Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (URANS) are employed separately or in combination with Computational Aero-Acoustics (CAA) simulations to quantify noise levels for high-fidelity [3, 4, 5]. In addition, such advanced simulation results are quantified with measurements using dynamic model decomposition or principal orthogonal decomposition techniques. However, these methods demand more resources and time.

The prominent work of Tyler and Sofrin [6] is the only analytical approach known in the literature for designing turbomachinery components for reducing interaction noise transmission, such as rotor stator interaction or gust interaction with rotor, etc. However, this method cannot be used for rotor-alone noise transmission. Even though a lot of literature can be found related to transmitted noise and its reduction techniques using passive noise control devices, very little literature is found related to noise generated at the source [2,5].

Stéphane discusses the use of analytical models in axial turbomachinery tonal noise prediction using strip theory and a mode-matching approach in bifurcated waveguides (MMBW). Both of these methods are based on the assumption of linear acoustics for predicting far field noise. The literature does not

directly employ analytical models for predicting noise from centrifugal compressors [7].

The above mentioned methods are either cumbersome and/or time consuming to be included into a design system for designing turbocharger compressors as design iterations need to be far more quicker than the time taken for carrying out detailed measurements in acoustic test cells or performing high-fidelity simulations.

In this context, this paper deals with identifying a parameter, namely, the acoustic crest factor, that can indicate the tonal BPF noise levels using RANS simulations. Acoustic crest factor values correlate with sound pressure level measurements from experimental tests at varied operating conditions. In addition, the acoustic crest factor has been used to rank four different compressor designs tested experimentally in an anechoic chamber.

2. METHODS

Sound energy is transported as waves in air (medium) without transporting matter. The Blade Pass Frequency (BPF) noise generated from a compressor is mainly due to the unsteady blade loading that acts as an excitation source of the sound waves generated and transmitted by the impeller and other components of the compressor. In this study, the BPF noise (sound waves) generated at the downstream of the impeller are studied in detail using experimental testing and numerical simulations. Two types of impellers (Figure 1), namely, a full-blade and a splitter-blade impeller, are used for this study as they are prominently used in turbochargers.

In a full-blade arrangement, the leading edges at the blades' hub start at the same axial position. In a splitter-blade impeller arrangement, the leading edges at the hub of every other blade begin at a later position axially, compared to the neighboring blades. Splitter configuration is generally preferred to have a wider range of mass flow due to a comparatively lower blockage of the blades. Figure 2 shows a typical compressor map with pressure ratio along the ordinate and corrected mass flow rate along the abscissa. The contours on the plot indicate the wheel inlet relative Mach number calculated from the static and total pressures measured at the inlet section of the compressor.

Full Blade Impeller

Splitter Blade Impeller

Figure 1: Compressor Impellers: Full-blade (Left) and Splitter-blade (Right)

Figure 2: Compressor Map for a Full-blade wheel Compressor stage

In order to compare experimental and numerical results, 3 tip speeds namely, 380 m/s, 499 m/s and 565 m/s are chosen as they cover subsonic, transonic and supersonic inlet relative Mach numbers on the compressor map.

2.1 Numerical Modelling

Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) simulations were carried out for 3 tip speeds mentioned above for both full-blade and splitter-blade configurations. The circumferential static pressure variation were obtained from a sectional plane close to the exit of the impeller (shown in Figure 4). This evaluation plane is positioned as close as possible to the measurement location of the unsteady static pressure probe in the tests.

The simulation model includes an inlet, two types of impellers and a vaneless diffuser. Volute is not included due to the complexities involved in both the unstructured meshing of

the volute geometry and the comparatively longer duration taken for the RANS solutions to converge. Also, only a single channel of the compressor impeller for the full-blade wheel and two consecutive channels, including a splitter and a full-blade for the splitter-blade wheel, are simulated for faster results. Other details about the numerical setup is described in the table below. For more details on the process of mesh validation, the readers are referred to an earlier publication [8].

Simulation Feature	Solver Settings
Type of solver	Finite-volume, density-based solver
Averaging process for virtual monitors	Area averaging for pressure, Mass flow averaging for efficiency
Mesh Type	Structured mesh
Governing Equation	RANS
Turbulence model	Spalart-Almaras
Discretization Scheme	Third-order upwinding
Numerical Scheme	Implicit Gauss-Siedel

Table 1: Numerical setup

The numerical modelling approach used here is a simple steady state RANS approach using a Spalart-Almaras turbulence model. A frozen rotor interface treatment has been applied in this study, wherein the flow field from the impeller is transported to the diffuser without any averaging, preserving the circumferential characteristics of flow field. The fillets on the impeller blades were not included to reduce the meshing complexity involved. The diffuser walls were prescribed isothermal boundary conditions to avoid heat transfer effects. The entropy generation from the back face losses at the impeller exit is not included in the model.

In the numerical setup (Table 1), an evaluation plane (Figure 3) extends on either side of the blade halfway through the width of the channel on the full-blade wheel. For the splitter-blade wheel, both passages, including a full-blade and a splitter-blade, are used for evaluation. This evaluation plane is positioned at the hub and at an appropriate streamwise position, as close to the physical location of the unsteady pressure sensor as possible to extract time-mean static pressure data.

Figure 3: Evaluation Plane – RANS CFD

2.2 Experimental Setup

In addition to numerical simulations, experimental measurements were carried out on both the splitter and full-blade wheels. The experimental method used for this work comprises of an aerodynamic and an acoustic setup. The aerodynamic setup includes a detailed set of static and total pressure, temperature measurements across the centrifugal compressor components as shown in Figure 4 and Table 2. The acoustic setup comprises of fast pressure transducers at varied locations in order to characterize the component level tonal noise contribution. A miniature high temperature ruggedized pressure transducer is used for unsteady pressure measurements[11].

The test has been carried out on two centrifugal compressors, one with a full-blade shroudless radial impeller, and the other with a splitter-blade shroudless radial impeller, a common compressor housing consisting of a vaneless diffuser and an overhung volute mounted in a gas stand. The compressors were tested at different operating conditions in terms of mass flow, pressure ratio, and tip speeds. The gas stand is not an anechoic acoustic test chamber but has been adopted to carry out acoustic measurements for turbocharger compressors based on the instrumentation suggested by ISO 3744. A detailed procedure for this type of adaptation, measurement and validation is elaborated here[12].

Figure 4: Compressor cross-section showing measurement planes

Number & Type of Measurement	Station
3xP ₁ , 3xT ₀₁	1
1xP _{u2}	2
1xP _{u3}	3
20xP ₄ , 1xP ₀₄	4
20xP ₅ , 1xP ₀₅	5
1xP _{u6}	6
1xP ₇	7
1xP _{u8}	8
3xP ₉ , 3xT ₀₉	9

Table 2: Measurement setup

For more details on the aerodynamics setup, the readers are referred to earlier publications [8,9,10]. The Sound Pressure Level (SPL) values are later calculated using the following equation (1).

$$SPL = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{P'_{uxh}}{P_{ref}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where, P'_{uxh} is the measured rms pressure fluctuations from the fast pressure transducers measuring unsteady pressure and p_{ref} is the reference pressure of air (20 μ Pa). The sampling frequency used during this measurement was 50 kHz, which allows enough

margin for the highest frequency to be measured according to the Nyquist criterion. Since this work focuses on the BPF spectrum of centrifugal impeller acoustics, SPL values are calculated for corresponding BPF values using the formula below. ‘Z’ is the number of blades and ‘N’ is the rotational speed of the compressor impeller in rotations per minute.

$$BPF = Z * \frac{N}{60} \quad (2)$$

In order to validate the concept presented in this work, in an acoustic non-reflective anechoic chamber, the concept was applied to four different impeller designs that were designed, manufactured and tested in the acoustic test cell. The experimental setup for this anechoic acoustic test cell includes the turbocharger mounted on a six-cylinder diesel engine, a series of external microphones according to ISO standard SS-EN_ISO_3745_2012 and order tracking using LMS system. This acoustic test cell is well equipped with all the necessary instrumentation for measuring Sound Power Level (SWL) from turbocharger compressors.

Figure 5: Anechoic chamber for acoustic testing of Turbochargers

2.3 Unsteadiness in Turbomachines

There is a circumferential variation of static pressure at the exit of the impeller as seen in Figure 12 extracted from RANS simulations. This is due to the fact that there is an inherent unsteadiness in the flow passing through a moving cascade in a turbomachine, even though most problems related to turbomachinery flows are being solved using steady flow equations and their corresponding assumptions. The impeller of a centrifugal compressor is the only component of the stage wherein a change in total enthalpy occurs. The time rate of change in total enthalpy in the impeller demands a temporal variation of static pressure of the flow passing through the impeller in the absolute frame of reference. As shown in equations 3 and 4, this temporal variation of static pressure in the absolute frame is related to the circumferential variation of static pressure in the relative frame of reference and the corresponding blade speed [13,14,15]. This, in fact, is the unsteady blade loading that every impeller blade experiences during its operation.

$$\left. \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \right|_{\text{abs}} = r\omega \left. \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \theta} \right|_{\text{rel}} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{DP_0}{Dt} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = \left[r\omega \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \theta} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

Thus, the circumferential variation of static pressure $\left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial \theta} \right)$ at the impeller exit could be used to correlate the temporal variation of static pressure $\left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \right)$ for a given blade speed. Also, since the time-mean static pressure evaluation is carried out close to the impeller exit, the sound field variation generated by the impeller can be studied in detail, where the secondary effects of acoustic propagation, transmission and reflection are negligible [2].

2.4 Acoustic Crest Factor

The concept of crest factor is widely used in signal processing [16] and is defined by the equation below.

$$\text{Acoustic Crest Factor} = \frac{\text{Peak value (p)}}{\text{RMS value (p)}} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{RMS Value (p)} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n p_i^2} \quad (6)$$

Crest factor is the ratio of a signal's peak value to the root mean square (RMS) value of the same signal. It indicates the amount of variation of the maximum or peak (crest) value from the RMS value of the signal. This captures the impulsiveness of the signal for a given energy content caused by the unsteady

blade loading. This impulsiveness is the forcing function generating noise. Hence, acoustic crest factor is used to quantify the acoustic characteristics of the impeller exit noise and hence the name, acoustic crest factor.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The full and splitter-blade wheels considered for this work were tested in a turbocharger test rig to characterize the aerodynamic performance of the stage at a component level. Later, these two compressors were instrumented with fast pressure transducers to characterize the acoustic signatures related to BPF noise at a component level. Finally, a correlation between the SPL of the BPF order at the impeller exit and the acoustic crest factor of circumferential variation of static pressure at the impeller exit at varied speeds are discussed in detail for both the splitter and full-blade wheels. Finally, the acoustic crest factor method is applied to four different compressor designs to rank them acoustically and tested in an anechoic test chamber.

3.1 Aerodynamic validation

An aerodynamic validation of static pressure at impeller exit based on measured values and simulated data from RANS CFD is presented here. Figure 6 shows the comparison of static pressure between measurements and simulations for all the three tip speeds. The closest match between simulated results from CFD and test data is observed at 380 m/s and the difference between them increases with increasing tip speeds. A maximum difference of static pressure (15%) is observed at the highest tip speed (565 m/s) for the full-blade wheel. Even though the absolute difference between measurement and simulation can be considered high at a few operating points, the trends of static pressure rise curves are fairly the same between measurements and simulations at all tip speeds.

The pressure rise characteristics on a radial impeller stem from the combination of work input and efficiency characteristics. This indicates a crucial concept that the impeller efficiency has changed between test and CFD as the work input characteristics are coupled to the backswept trailing edge, which remained unchanged. The impeller efficiency differs from the predictions of CFD at tip speeds 499 m/s and 565 m/s as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Comparison of Static pressure measured in Test and CFD simulations – Full-blade Wheel.

Figure 7: Comparison of total-to-total wheel efficiency measured in Test and CFD simulations – Full-blade Wheel.

The impeller total-to-total efficiencies from CFD and measured test data are plotted in the figure above. At the tip speed of 380 m/s, the impeller efficiencies from test are predicted well by the CFD results. However, with increasing tip speeds, the impeller efficiency predicted by CFD is higher than that measured. One reason is the lack of fillets in the CFD model and the other simplifications that do not account for the losses in reality. The other reason is the thermal expansion of the compressor cover during tests, which could have caused an efficiency drop that could not be modelled in CFD.

Figure 8 shows a similar comparison for the splitter-blade wheel. As discussed earlier, the pressure rise characteristics are similar between CFD and test results confirming that the work input characteristics are conserved. A maximum difference of static pressure (17%) is observed at the highest tip speed (565 m/s). The pressure rise characteristics between test and CFD for

all tip speeds are similar to the results observed for the full-blade impeller.

Figure 8: Comparison of Static pressure measured in Test and CFD simulations – Splitter-blade Wheel.

Figure 9 shows the corresponding total-to-total efficiency characteristics for the splitter-blade wheel. Here, the mismatch in efficiency is seen at all the three tip speeds and a comparatively higher variation in efficiency close to surge than that seen in the full-blade wheel results. Also, there is a non-monotonic behavior in the efficiency curves from the test, close to surge and choke along the tip speed 380 m/s and surge region along 499 m/s. The curvature of the efficiency characteristics measured are completely different from the ones predicted by CFD. Interestingly, this type of non-monotonicity is not observed in the corresponding static pressure measurements shown in Figure 8.

Figure 9: Comparison of total-to-total wheel efficiency measured in Test and CFD simulations – Splitter-blade Wheel. Vertical bars show hub to shroud variation of efficiency

3.2 Acoustic quantification

The impeller of a radial compressor is the only work producing component and is the main source of noise generation. Results from acoustic measurement data illustrating a component-level noise contribution at a specific tip speed (565 m/s) indicate that impeller exit noise is the major source for both splitter and full-blade designs (Figure 10 & Figure 11) on a majority of the operating points (from surge to choke-left to right) for the considered tip speed. The impeller exit contribution is higher compared to other noise sources, namely, impeller inlet, diffuser exit and volute exit.

Figure 10: Component level Full-blade BPF noise at 565 m/s

Figure 11: Component level Splitter-blade BPF noise at 565 m/s

Figure 12 shows the circumferential variation of static pressure across a single blade passage in the circumferential direction of the full-blade wheel extracted from the evaluation plane in the RANS simulation. Since the unsteady pressure measurements in the acoustic test were carried out on the hub side, the static pressure signal in the RANS simulations is extracted from the nodes closest to the hub.

Figure 12: Circumferential variation of the hub static pressure at impeller exit evaluation plane from RANS (CFD)

3.3 Aero-Acoustic correlation

Acoustic crest factor of the static pressure signals are calculated at varied operating points on the compressor map for the three tip speeds chosen earlier using equation 5. In addition, the measured impeller exit BPF sound pressure level (SPL) values are normalized and plotted for different operating points along the corresponding tip speed line. The SPL values are normalized using the average SPL value of impeller inlet on the splitter-blade at 499 m/s. These values of acoustic crest factor and normalized SPL for the tip speeds 380, 499 and 565 m/s for both full and splitter-blade wheels are plotted in Figure 13 to Figure 20. In addition, a moving average of order 3 is also plotted on the normalized SPL values in order to emphasize the underlying trends in the data.

Figure 13: Normalized SPL and Acoustic Crest Factor at 380 m/s – Full-blade impeller

For the tip speed 380 m/s, corresponding to a subsonic Mach number at the impeller inlet, it is observed that the Acoustic Crest Factor values of static pressure at the impeller exit have a bucket-like behavior with a minimum close to the stall region and increases monotonically beyond a mass flow rate of 0.32 kg/s (Figure 13). The moving average curve provides a more detailed insight into the underlying trends. The normalized SPL values from the test also exhibit a bucket-like behavior and monotonicity in the similar mass flow range as the acoustic crest factor values. This indicates a strong correlation between the trend of acoustic crest factor of circumferential variation of static pressure with normalized SPL, along the operating speed line. The impeller exit noise tends to be at a minimum at the middle of the speed line and increases along both surge and choke regions. The extent of increase in crest factor is lower towards the surge region when comparing to the normalized SPL values.

Figure 14: Normalized SPL and Acoustic Crest Factor at 499 m/s – Full-blade impeller

In Figure 14, the acoustic crest factor and the normalized SPL values for a tip speed of 499 m/s (transonic inlet Mach number) are plotted for a full-blade impeller. The values of acoustic crest factor for the entire speed line are higher than the values deduced for the lower tip speed of 380 m/s. The acoustic crest factor of static pressure has a clear minima close to the mass flow rate of 0.45 kg/s and tends to increase away from this point both towards the choke and surge regions. A similar behavior is seen in the normalized SPL curve, where the minimum is shifted towards the choke region closer to 0.5 kg/s. Even though there is a difference in the position of minima between the test and CFD results, the trends in the curves indicate a similar acoustic phenomenon: the impeller exit noise increases more towards choke than surge at this tip speed. The impeller total-to-total efficiency plots (Figure 7) indicate a difference between CFD and test data at 0.5 kg/s. The reason for this shift in minima at 0.5 kg/s, indicated by the efficiency difference could be due to

the deflection of the compressor cover, thereby causing a reduction in unsteady blade loading (discussed in section 3.1), reducing impeller exit noise. The last two points on the acoustic crest factor are well within the deep choke region and can be ignored.

Figure 15: Normalized SPL and Acoustic Crest Factor at 565 m/s – Full-blade impeller

For the tip speed 565 m/s, corresponding to supersonic Mach number at the impeller inlet, it is observed that the acoustic crest factor values of static pressure at the impeller exit are fairly constant till a mass flow rate of 0.58 kg/s and increases beyond it, close to the choke region (Figure 15). The normalized SPL values have a similar behavior from surge to choke indicated by the moving average line. Even though there is a difference in impeller efficiency between test and CFD (Figure 7), possibly due to compressor cover deflection, this does not affect the acoustic behavior here at the tip speed of 565 m/s.

For the splitter-blade impeller arrangement, a similar comparison of acoustic crest factor and normalized SPL for the three tip speeds chosen earlier is plotted in Figure 16 to Figure 20. Overall, the acoustic crest factor values increase with increasing tip speeds, due to the higher amplitudes of static pressures with increasing tip speeds. For the tip speed of 380 m/s (Figure 16), the crest factor values do not follow the trend shown by normalized SPL close to surge (below 0.3 kg/s). It is interesting to note from the aerodynamic validation plot (Figure 9) that the impeller efficiency starts to decrease at 0.3 kg/s, indicating the onset of positive incidence on the blades. With mass flows increasing beyond 0.3 kg/s, the acoustic crest factor predicts the trends of the moving average of the normalized SPL well.

Figure 16: Normalized SPL and Acoustic Crest Factor at 380 m/s – Splitter-blade impeller

A similar trend mismatch between acoustic crest factor and normalized SPL is observed at the tip speed of 499 m/s (Figure 17), with the onset of positive incidence (below 0.45 kg/s). Beyond the mass flow of 0.45 kg/s, the trends of normalized SPL and acoustic crest factor tend to match well. The effect of compressor cover deflection and the consequence of reduction in blade loading could be seen in the slight decrease of normalized SPL close to the mass flow rate of 0.48 kg/s but it is not as pronounced as in the full-blade impeller.

Figure 17: Normalized SPL and Acoustic Crest Factor at 499 m/s – Splitter-blade impeller

For both the tip speeds (380 and 499 m/s), the increase in positive incidence, indicated by the drop in impeller efficiency, causes a tip vortex (Figure 18) that grows in strength

with increasing incidence and interacts with the leading edge of the splitter-blade, causing noise. Figure 19 shows the contour plot of relative Mach number showing a cross section of the vortex interaction (marked by a red dashed line) between leading edge of the main and splitter blades. Even though this is captured in the RANS CFD, the exact running tip clearance in the test is higher than the tip clearance modelled in the RANS simulations, due to thermal inertia. This means that the tip vortex in reality is much stronger than that predicted by the RANS simulations and hence the corresponding tip vortex interaction noise is not accounted for in the circumferential pressure variation at the trailing edge and hence not indicated by the acoustic crest factor. The presence of such a tip vortex and the associated tip vortex interaction noise is sparsely found in the open literature [17, 18]. The running tip clearance should be modeled accurately in order to quantify this effect. In addition, the acoustic crest factor can be applied at the inlet of the impeller, close to the shroud to investigate its correlation with normalized SPL. If both, the correct tip clearance and impeller inlet acoustic crest factor do not correlate with the normalized SPL, then it is a result of a purely acoustic phenomenon.

Figure 18: Tip vortex interaction between leading edge of main blade to leading edge of splitter-blade, recreated from [18]

Figure 19: Relative Mach number at 0.44 kg/s, 499 m/s – Splitter-blade impeller

Figure 20 shows the acoustic crest factor increases linearly and then stays almost constant between mass flows 0.58 to 0.6 kg/s and then increases again, neglecting the last three

points in deep choke. The trends between acoustic crest factor and normalized SPL values at 565 m/s do not match. However, the acoustic crest factor can still predict the increase in impeller exit noise close to choke region.

Figure 20: Normalized SPL and Acoustic Crest Factor at 565 m/s – Splitter-blade impeller

Overall, for the splitter-blade arrangement, acoustic crest factor values show an increasing trend from surge to choke, while the SPL values show a non-monotonic behavior at all tip speeds.

Based on the comparisons shown above, the acoustic crest factor can be applied to both full and splitter-blade arrangements of the impeller. It is to be noted that the absolute value of acoustic crest factor increases with increasing tip speeds (subsonic to supersonic flow regimes), which is an indication of the increasing amplitude of the pressure signals. The acoustic crest factor values predict a higher noise level at the choke compared to surge region and this is clearly seen in the normalized SPL values at all speed lines for both full and splitter-blade wheels. This elucidates that acoustic crest factor of static pressure at the exit of the impeller can be used to indicate BPF noise levels at the impeller exit. However, the impeller exit BPF prediction seems to be better for the full-blade arrangement compared to the splitter-blade impeller, especially for the mass flow rates from lower than that at the onset of positive incidence for all tip speeds.

3.3 Validation

In order to validate the concept of ranking designs with acoustic crest factor, this method was tested on four different centrifugal compressor impeller designs with splitter blades. The operating conditions were close to middle of the compressor map, towards the positive incidence side, at transonic flow

regime with a tip speed of 484 m/s. These were manufactured and tested in an anechoic chamber shown in Figure 5. These tests were carried out in an acoustic test cell, wherein the Sound Power Level (SWL) was measured using external microphones, detailed in the final part of section 2.2. The Sound Power level measurement is a robust parameter to quantify the acoustic signature of a noise source, as it measures the acoustic intensity from a source. Figure 21 shows a plot of acoustic crest factor values of static pressures from RANS CFD plotted along the abscissa and sound power level in decibels plotted along the ordinate.

Figure 21: SWL and Acoustic Crest Factor for four compressor designs

Based on the results, it was observed that using the acoustic crest factor, one can rank the four different designs in the same way as in an anechoic chamber. As discussed earlier, impeller exit noise is a major contributor to the overall noise level from the compressor and since acoustic crest factor can predict the impeller exit noise, the above ranking of different impeller designs could be obtained.

Since the impeller exit BPF acoustic behavior are correlated to the acoustic crest factor of the circumferential variation of static pressure at the impeller exit, this can be used as a design tool for prediction purposes. Since this acoustic crest factor method uses simple and comparatively quick RANS simulations, this can be exploited to rank different designs at a very early stage of the design lifecycle. This method is a simple, faster and easier solution for evaluation, ranking and design/redesign of centrifugal impellers for exit BPF noise. In addition, minimization of the acoustic crest factor values at the impeller exit can be used as an objective for optimization exercises.

3.4 Limitations

Here, we enumerate some of the limitations of this method of using acoustic crest factor to predict impeller exit BPF noise.

- 1) Absolute value of impeller exit BPF noise, both SPL and SWL cannot be determined using this method.
- 2) This method is limited to tonal noise level predictions and its validity has not been evaluated for broadband noise.
- 3) This method predicts the impeller exit BPF noise generated at source and has not been evaluated for prediction of transmitted noise through ducts.
- 4) Tip vortex interaction noise cannot be predicted by acoustic crest factor.

4. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) A correlation between the circumferential variation of static pressure at the outlet of the impeller to the temporal variation of static pressure at the impeller exit is observed based on CFD and experiments.
- 2) Acoustic crest factor of the circumferential variation of static pressure at impeller exit can be used as a parameter to indicate impeller exit BPF for both full and splitter-blade arrangements.
- 3) For a full-blade wheel, Acoustic crest factor increases from subsonic to supersonic regimes and for a given tip speed, it is lower at the middle of the speed line and increases towards surge and choke regions, as indicated by sound pressure levels from measurements at the impeller exit.
- 4) With the data obtained from the tests and CFD, Acoustic crest factor predicts the impeller exit BPF of full-blade impeller better than the splitter-blade impeller, especially for regions at the onset of positive incidence to surge on a compressor map due to a tip vortex interaction.
- 5) Using the acoustic crest factor, different compressor designs can be ranked acoustically. This is validated with tests carried out on four different compressor impellers (splitter-blade) in an anechoic test chamber. Hence, acoustic crest factor can be used as a design tool to rank different impeller designs.

5. Future Work

As indicated, for the splitter-blade impeller, the running tip clearance should be modelled properly to quantify its effect on acoustic crest factor. Since, the effect of tip vortex is prominent at the leading edge of the impeller, this method can be applied to the inlet of the impeller at the shroud to verify the correlation. Further, the concept of acoustic crest factor can be applied to inlet sections (with and without ported shroud, noise baffle), impeller inlet and outlet, diffuser (vaned and vaneless), volute (overhung, symmetrical) or any channels connecting these

components of the radial compressor to understand its correlation with unsteady blade loading. Since this concept works based on the quantification of the unsteady blade loading, this concept could be applied to any turbomachine and their components such as axial compressors, turbines, axial fans, centrifugal fans and any other turbomachine that has a cascade of blades. In addition, this concept could be explored further for propellers used for varied applications and their blade sections.

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